

1 The Food Contact Chemicals Health Effect Matrix

2 (FCChelix): Protocol for a systematic evidence map

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24 Abstract

25 *Background:* Food contact chemicals (FCCs) are known to migrate from food packaging
26 and other food contact articles into food. This leads to human exposure to FCCs, and
27 some FCCs have been linked to human health effects such as chronic and non-
28 communicable diseases. However, a systematic overview of the health effects of FCCs
29 is missing.

30 *Objectives:* The objective of this study is to systematically map the relations between
31 exposure to FCCs and human health effects within the Population, Exposure,
32 Comparator, Outcomes, and Study Design (PECOS) framework.

33 *Search strategy and eligibility criteria:* We will search PubMed for combinations of
34 search terms related to the identity of the chemical and the epidemiological study
35 design. The references will be screened at title and abstract level, followed by full-text
36 level. Eligible references will be included according to predefined criteria, further
37 specifying the elements of the applied PECOS framework.

38 *Data extraction and coding:* Information on human exposure to FCCs will be collected
39 and linked to human health effects according to previously defined data categories and
40 standardized terms. The human health effects will be classified based on the Six
41 Clusters of Disease (SCOD) framework.

42 *Synthesis and visualization:* Results will be published in a narrative summary and data
43 will be made available in a freely accessible interactive dashboard, the Food Contact
44 Chemicals Health Effect Matrix (FCChelix).

45 Introduction

46 Rationale

47 Humans are exposed to many synthetic chemicals from various sources, and exposure
48 to some of these chemicals has been linked to the rise of non-communicable diseases
49 (Martínez-Ibarra et al., 2021; Symeonides et al., 2024). Food packaging and other food
50 contact articles (FCAs) contribute to this exposure via oral uptake because food contact
51 chemicals (FCCs) migrate from food contact materials (FCMs) into foodstuffs (Muncke
52 et al., 2020).

53 Regulating FCMs and managing the risks associated with chemical migration from
54 FCMs is challenging. Firstly, hundreds of FCCs with hazard properties of concern are
55 used in FCMs (Zimmermann et al., 2022) and legislation often lags far behind
56 toxicological research (Muncke et al., 2017). Secondly, many FCCs do not have
57 sufficient migration, hazard, and exposure data to assess their risks, and this is even
58 more pronounced for non-intentionally added substances (NIAS), such as degradation
59 products, contaminants, impurities, and by-products (Nerin et al., 2013; Nerín et al.,
60 2022).

61 To understand which FCCs are used in the manufacture of FCMs, we previously
62 compiled the Food Contact Chemicals Database (FCCdb), listing publicly available
63 evidence on >12,000 intentionally used FCCs (Groh et al., 2021). However, during FCM
64 manufacturing, many intentionally used FCCs are chemically transformed, leading to
65 the generation of expected reaction products as well as NIAS. To better understand
66 which chemicals are present in FCMs, we also published a systematic evidence map on
67 FCCs that have been analyzed in migrates and/or extracts of FCMs (Geueke et al.,
68 2023). The resulting Database on Migrating and Extractable Food Contact Chemicals
69 (FCCmigex) is available as an interactive dashboard (Food Packaging Forum, 2025).
70 FCCmigex currently contains information on 5,295 FCCs from 1,500 references.
71 Together, the FCCdb and FCCmigex databases include >15,000 FCCs, but the overlap
72 between them is small, as only 28% of the FCCs detected in migrates and/or extracts
73 are also part of the FCCdb. The remaining 72% of the chemicals in the FCCmigex

74 database may be present as NIAS or may have been used intentionally without being
75 listed in the sources included in the FCCdb. Migration from FCMs indicates a high
76 probability of human exposure, albeit with some uncertainty. To understand the extent
77 of human exposure to FCCs, we systematically compiled the Database on Food
78 Contact Chemicals Monitored in Humans (FCChumon) (Food Packaging Forum, 2024;
79 Geueke, Parkinson, et al., 2024). In total, 25% of the known FCCs have been detected in
80 humans. While not dismissing exposure sources other than FCMs, these data
81 nonetheless help to link exposure from FCMs to the presence of FCCs in humans, and
82 they also support the identification of knowledge gaps. The FCCdb, FCCmigex, and
83 FCChumon databases provide systematically compiled information on the use of FCCs
84 in the manufacture of FCMs as well as their presence in migrates and/or extracts of
85 FCMs and in human samples. However, comprehensive data on human health effects
86 exist for only a small fraction of these chemicals. For example, the Plastic Health Map
87 summarizes human health effects of selected plastic-associated chemicals and
88 particles, including polymers, plasticizers, flame retardants, bisphenols, and per- and
89 polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) (Minderoo Foundation; Seewoo et al., 2023). Further
90 systematic evidence maps and scoping reviews associating chemical exposure and
91 human health outcomes have been published, such as on bisphenol A (Zhu et al.,
92 2024), PFAS (Pelch et al., 2022; Radke et al., 2022; Ricolfi et al., 2024; Shirke et al.,
93 2024; Zhang et al., 2023), polyethylene terephthalate (PET) oligomers (Schreier et al.,
94 2023), and persistent organic pollutants (Carlson et al., 2023; Payne-Sturges et al.,
95 2023; Yost et al., 2021). A recent umbrella review focused on selected plastic-related
96 exposures to chemicals across a broad range of groups and identified at least one
97 adverse health outcome for each group (Symeonides et al., 2024). Based on a gap
98 analysis, the authors of the umbrella review prioritized micro- and nanoplastics,
99 bisphenol analogues, non-phthalate plasticizers, and alternative flame retardants as
100 key priority areas for further research. For other chemical groups broadly used in FCMs,
101 such as synthetic phenolic antioxidants, studies on human health effects are scarce
102 (Hao et al., 2023).

103 Recent regulatory actions addressed the health risks of certain chemical groups by
104 establishing legally enforceable limits on, e.g., PFAS in food packaging waste (EU
105 2025/40) and bisphenols in FCMs (EU 2024/3190).

106 However, many current regulatory approaches to chemical risk assessment for FCCs
107 primarily emphasize evaluating the genotoxicity of chemicals used as starting
108 substances in the production of FCMs. This neglects the presence of NIAS in FCMs and
109 other toxicological endpoints that are also of high concern. One notable development is
110 the recent regulatory amendment on plastic FCMs (EU 2025/351) that introduced more
111 details on the required risk assessment of NIAS in the EU.

112 In 2023, chronic health outcomes that are highly prevalent in the human population
113 were grouped into Six Clusters of Disease (SCOD), including cancers, cardiovascular
114 diseases, reproductive disorders, brain-related disorders, immunological disorders, and
115 metabolic diseases (Figure 1) (Muncke et al., 2023). To better understand the impact of
116 FCCs on human health, the development of high-throughput screening assays for
117 endpoints related to these disease clusters was recommended. Such high-throughput
118 methods would allow testing of all migrating FCCs. However, it is also essential to
119 understand the epidemiologic data linking exposure to FCCs to diseases categorized
120 under the SCOD framework. This knowledge can support the development of screening
121 assays.

122
123 Figure 1. The Six Clusters of Disease (SCOD) concept comprises highly-prevalent, non-
124 communicable diseases that are of increasing concern and associated with hazardous
125 chemical exposures (according to (Muncke et al., 2023)).

126 Objectives

127 Our aim is to systematically map the literature examining the established links between
128 exposure to known FCCs and adverse human health outcomes. We will particularly
129 focus on FCCs that have been detected in FCMs and in human samples (Geueke et al.,
130 2023; Geueke, Parkinson, et al., 2024). Health outcomes will be assigned to the SCOD
131 (Figure 1) (Muncke et al., 2023). The international classification of diseases (11th
132 revision, ICD-11; (World Health Organisation, 2022)) will be used as basis for these
133 assignments.

134 The systematic evidence map will allow the identification of FCCs (i) that are associated
135 with human health effects and (ii) for which more data on exposure and/or health
136 effects are needed. Additionally, it aims to provide information for more specific
137 research questions that are, for example, related to certain chemicals or chemical
138 groups, types of FCMs, specific health outcomes, or vulnerable populations. The data
139 will be presented in an interactive and openly accessible dashboard, the **Food Contact**
140 **Chemicals Health Effect Matrix (FCChelix)**, and key findings will be summarized in a
141 peer-reviewed article.

142 Methods

143 This protocol was drafted following the updated 2015 PRISMA-P guidelines (Preferred
144 Reporting Items for Systematic review and Meta-Analysis Protocols; Annex 3) (Moher et
145 al., 2015; Page et al., 2021) and giving due consideration to the recommendations for
146 the Conduct of Systematic Reviews in Toxicology and Environmental Health Research
147 (COSTER) (Whaley et al., 2020).

148 Research question

149 The PECOS (Population, Exposure, Comparator, Outcome, Study Design) framework will
150 be applied to answer the research question: Which FCCs are associated with non-
151 communicable chronic diseases in humans? (Table 1).

152 Table 1. Elements of the research question following the PECOS framework.

Element of PECOS framework	Description
Population	Any human
Exposure	To FCCs or metabolites of FCCs
Comparator	Control groups or any other comparator
Outcome	Human health effects related to the Six Clusters of Disease (SCOD)
Study design	Epidemiological studies

153 Eligibility criteria

154 Inclusion and exclusion criteria are defined to facilitate decisions on the eligibility of a
 155 reference during literature screening (Table 2). They are structured according to the
 156 elements of the PECOS framework. Studies meeting one or more exclusion criteria will
 157 be excluded. Eligible studies contain primary data, have been peer-reviewed, and are
 158 published in English. There will be no general restriction regarding the publication date.

159 The systematic evidence map will consider studies on any human *population* globally,
 160 without restrictions on age, sex, life stage, and pre-existing health conditions. Studies
 161 on animals and human cell lines will be excluded. Data from a control group are
 162 included in the study, serving as *comparator*.

163 Studies are required to report the detection of FCCs in human samples (indicating
 164 *exposure*) and link them to human health effects. We will only consider epidemiological
 165 studies on FCCs that have been previously detected in migrates and/or extracts of FCMs
 166 (Food Packaging Forum, 2025). For some FCCs, specific metabolites are known and
 167 routinely assessed (e.g., phthalates). If such metabolites have been detected in
 168 humans, the exposure element of the framework is fulfilled.

169 Only measurements of human health effects will be included. The health *outcomes* can
 170 be classified into at least one of these six disease clusters (i.e., SCOD): cancers,
 171 cardiovascular diseases, reproductive disorders, brain-related disorders,
 172 immunological disorders, and metabolic diseases (Figure 1). Studies reporting the
 173 diagnoses of a disease will be included (e.g., diabetes), as well as studies on
 174 physiological and/or biochemical measurement that are associated with changes in

175 relevant organ systems (e.g., ovaries, brain). A longitudinal or cross-sectional *study*
 176 *design* is required; case reports will be excluded.

177 Table 2. Elements of the PECOS framework and eligibility criteria to be applied during literature
 178 screening. Studies that meet any exclusion criteria will not be considered eligible.

Element of PECOS framework	Inclusion	Exclusion
Population	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any human, without restriction based on age, sex, life stage, and preexisting health conditions, including the developing fetus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analyzed sample originates from an animal, plant, fungi, and bacteria, is an environmental sample, or is not defined • Sample is a human cell line
Exposure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analyzed sample originates from a human specimen (e.g., blood, urine, breast milk) AND at least one analyte is an FCC that has previously been detected in extracts/migrates of FCMs (i.e., the chemical is listed in the FCCmigex database) or a specific metabolite of such an FCC (i.e., the parent compound is specifically transformed into the analyte) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FCC or its specific metabolite is listed in the FCCdb, but has never been detected in migrates or extracts of FCMs according to the FCCmigex database • Modelling of chemical exposure • Dermal exposure, such as patch and skin-prick tests
Comparator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All studies including a control group or any other comparator 	
Outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any health outcome that can be related to the Six Clusters of Disease (SCOD) • Direct reporting of a disease 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Missing/incomplete assessment of health outcome • Health outcome cannot be aligned with SCOD • Modelling of health outcomes

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measurement of physiological and/or biochemical changes associated with the SCOD 	
Study design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Epidemiological studies including longitudinal or cross-sectional study designs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Case study/report • Descriptive studies

179 Stakeholder engagement

180 During the development of this protocol, we had regular meetings with the core team,
181 and the scientific advisory group (SAG) of the Food Contact Chemicals and human
182 Health (FCCH) project (Food Packaging Forum). The members of these two groups have
183 expertise in the fields of FCMs and FCCs, toxicology, epidemiology, chemical
184 databases, and systematic evidence mapping. Between August 2024 and January 2025,
185 we had monthly meetings with the core team. The core team has been deeply involved
186 in protocol development, literature screening and data extraction of previous
187 systematic evidence maps related to the FCCH project (i.e., FCCmigex and FCChumon)
188 (Geueke et al., 2023; Geueke, Parkinson, et al., 2024). Therefore, its members have a
189 detailed understanding of the underlying data and processes and provided valuable
190 input throughout the development of this protocol. All core team members are co-
191 authors of this protocol. Advice was also given by Louise Goodes from Minderoo
192 Foundation, who is the first author of the protocol of the Plastic Health Map (Goodes et
193 al., 2022). Additionally, the SAG of the FCCH project was consulted twice during
194 protocol development and asked for input during online meetings.

195 Information sources

196 We investigated the suitability of the databases PubMed, Medline (Ovid), Embiology®,
197 SciFinder®, and ScienceDirect® for this project. PubMed offers the most advantages in
198 terms of coverage of the literature, the possibility to run automated searches, and the
199 availability of search and filter options. Furthermore, PubMed is freely available and
200 focuses on medical/health related topics. As the use of only one database also
201 simplifies the workflow, data management and future updates for hundreds to
202 thousands of individual FCCs, PubMed will be used for all literature searches.

203 Search strategy

204 The ideal search strategy identifies as many relevant published studies on FCCs and
205 human health outcomes as reasonably feasible. However, the available evidence for
206 individual chemicals and chemical groups varies strongly. Therefore, we developed a
207 modular search strategy including study-related search terms, defined filter options,
208 and chemical-related search terms that will allow us to customize the literature
209 searches within given boundaries (Figure 2). This strategy is markedly different and less
210 complex than the searches employed by the Plastic Health Map (Seewoo et al., 2023).

211
212 Figure 2. Modular search strategy. Study-related search terms aim at identifying epidemiological
213 studies. Filter settings allow the selection of, e.g., the studied species (i.e., humans), publication
214 data and type and language. Chemical-related search terms include common chemical names,
215 synonyms and identifiers.

216 Scoping searches

217 We applied different strategies to identify search terms related to the study design of
218 epidemiological research. First, we brainstormed study-related search terms within the
219 core team and refined this list by running iterative searches. Then, we analyzed the word
220 frequencies of the reference titles included in the Plastic Health Map, as this
221 benchmark database addressed a similar research question regarding plastic-
222 associated chemicals in general (no specific focus on FCMs) (Seewoo et al., 2023).

223 Word frequency analysis was supported by using the Voyant tools (Sinclar et al., 2024).

224 Iterative testing of these preliminary terms resulted in a short and a long list of study-
225 related search terms (Table S1). We also applied different filter settings for the studied
226 species (i.e., human) and publication types. By combining the different study-related
227 search terms and filters, we obtained four search options and tested them for different
228 FCCs and groups of FCCs.

229 A comparison of the results of our scoping searches for bisphenols, phthalates, and
230 per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) with the benchmark references included in

231 the Plastic Health Map illustrated that our search options successfully captured 80-
232 97% of them (see Supplementary information, Figure S1). Refining of the chemical
233 related-search terms improved the coverage of a test search for PFAS from initially 50 to
234 92% (Figure S2). Importantly, in a preliminary screening of the reference list for
235 bisphenols, we identified even more eligible references that have not been included in
236 the Plastic Health Map (see Supplementary information, section 4). More detailed
237 analyses showed that most of the studies missed by the scoping searches are included
238 in PubMed but were not found because the chemical names are not mentioned in the
239 titles, abstracts or keywords (Figure S3). This limitation may be overcome by using
240 additional chemical synonyms. Based on the results of these scoping searches, we
241 considered our general search strategy to be appropriate in terms of sensitivity and
242 specificity.

243 **Implementing the literature searches**

244 Automated literature searches will be conducted in PubMed using the Entrez
245 Programming Utilities API. This approach will enable the systematic retrieval of records
246 for each FCC.

247 We will use the short list of study-related search terms as default setting, since it
248 balances sensitivity (i.e., identifying the benchmark references) and specificity (i.e.,
249 keeping the screening effort low) (search option 1, Table S1; Table 3).

250 In accordance with the eligibility criteria, the language filter for English and the
251 publication type “journal article” will be selected, and the publication types “review”
252 and “case report” will be excluded. The species filter for “humans” will be selected. No
253 date limit will be set. Only for FCCs that are already included in the Plastic Health Map,
254 we will search for references that were published after January 31, 2022 (i.e., the last
255 update of the Plastic Health Map). This will prevent duplication of work, as the Plastic
256 Health Map addressed a similar research question, and it is supported by the results of
257 our scoping exercise (see Supplementary Information).

258 Searching the scientific literature for individual chemicals is often challenging as
259 chemical names can have many different spellings and are often only mentioned in the
260 full text, tables and/or figures, which makes them undetectable in most literature

261 searches. Additionally, chemical identifiers such as CAS RN, InCHI and SMILES are
 262 rarely used in epidemiological studies. To address this and cover the chemical space
 263 more broadly, we will perform individual searches for each FCC and include names
 264 used in the FCC databases, CompTox, and CAS Common Chemistry, as well as IUPAC
 265 synonyms and CAS RNs (Geueke & Parkinson, 2024; Groh et al., 2022). Chemical
 266 synonyms and identifiers will be connected by the operator OR, as illustrated in Table 3.
 267 We will also search for groups of FCCs that have been assigned on the basis of similar
 268 functional or structural properties, because the group names may be mentioned in
 269 titles, abstracts, or keywords while individual chemical names may not. Work on the
 270 grouping of FCCs is currently ongoing at the Food Packaging Forum and will be
 271 applicable for this project.

272 Table 3. Search terms and filters to query for 1. an individual chemical (here: melamine) and 2. a
 273 chemical group (here: PFAS).

Study-related	Filters	Chemical-related (examples)
(NHANES OR HBM4EU OR CHMS OR KONEHS OR odds OR cross-sectional OR case-control OR cohort OR incidence OR prevalence OR epidemiol* OR associat* OR prospective OR longitudinal OR urin*)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Language: English • Publication type: "journal article" NOT "review" NOT "case report" • Species: human 	(melamine OR 108-78-1 OR "2,4,6-triamino-s-triazine") (PFAS OR perfluor* OR polyfluor*)

274

275 The potential for certain chemical names to yield unspecific results (e.g., "phenol"), and
 276 the possibility of missing studies due to the omission of commonly used chemical

277 synonyms may reduce the specificity and sensitivity of the search results, respectively.
278 These limitations will be acknowledged in the interpretation of the findings and
279 addressed, if possible, through iterative refinement of search terms. For example, if the
280 literature search for an FCC (group) of particular interest will not result in any eligible
281 references, we will consider conducting additional broader literature searches to make
282 sure that we did not miss relevant information. For chemicals where the search results
283 indicate many unspecific hits, searching only the titles and abstracts for the chemical
284 names may reduce the number of irrelevant studies.

285 Considerations on prioritizing FCCs

286 Scoping searches revealed substantial variability for individual chemicals and chemical
287 groups, ranging from zero to tens of thousands of studies found. This is mainly
288 attributed to the differences in the volume of existing research between chemicals. To
289 effectively address our research question and optimize the use of available resources,
290 we will

- 291 • focus on FCCs and groups of FCCs of particular interest (e.g., high evidence for
292 presence in FCMs, high level of concern),
- 293 • exclude FCCs for which there is widely recognized evidence linking chemical
294 exposure to human health effects (e.g., certain heavy metals and volatile organic
295 compounds, and pharmaceuticals found to present in FCMs), and
- 296 • exclude FCCs that are inorganic compounds, endogenous metabolites and/or
297 naturally occurring constituents of food.

298 By applying this prioritization strategy, we aim to focus on the most relevant FCCs that
299 are attributed to FCMs, while avoiding duplication of existing research.

300 Screening process

301 Duplicates within the search results will be identified based on their PubMed ID and
302 removed by using Excel, optionally followed by using the deduplication function in
303 SWIFT-Active Screener (Howard et al., 2020). For each reference, we will maintain the
304 links to the chemicals for which the respective studies have been found because this
305 information will facilitate data extraction.

306 All studies retrieved from the literature searches will be first screened in SWIFT-Active
307 Screener at title-and-abstract level, followed by full-text screening. The screening of the
308 titles and abstracts will be actively supported by SWIFT-Active Screener, which
309 iteratively prioritizes all references for manual screening. A 95% recall level will be set,
310 which defines the proportion of eligible studies to be included based on the prediction.
311 Studies that clearly do not meet all the inclusion criteria (Table 2) will be excluded
312 during either the title-and-abstract or the full-text screening. Initially, we will perform a
313 consistency check on 10% of the references at the title-and-abstract level to refine the
314 eligibility criteria, where two experts will screen in parallel. Disagreements will be
315 recorded, inter-rater reliability scores will be determined, and conflicts will be resolved.
316 Any learnings at this early screening stage will be included in a guidance document. If
317 the IRR score exceeds 0.7 at this stage, indicating acceptable agreement according to
318 (Hanegraaf et al., 2024), the remaining titles and abstracts will be screened
319 independently by one reviewer only. If the IRR is below 0.7, we will continue with parallel
320 screening for the next 10% of studies and then re-evaluate the IRR score. This process
321 will repeat until the IRR surpasses the threshold of 0.7, at which point single screening
322 will start, or the recall level predicted by SWIFT-Active Screener is reached and
323 screening can be stopped. All included references will then be screened at full-text level
324 and for consistency, ten percent of these will be screened independently and in parallel
325 by two team members. Any discrepancies will be resolved by bilateral discussions, with
326 the option to ask a third team member for their opinion. The IRR score will be tracked,
327 and we will follow the same process as described above for title-and-abstract
328 screening. A PRISMA flow diagram will be generated that provides an overview of the
329 studies found in the literature searches, how many of them were included/excluded at
330 the two different screening levels, and the reasons for exclusion at full text level (Figure
331 3).

332

333 Figure 3. Example workflow based on the PRISMA flow diagram. Individual literature searches
 334 will be run for each FCC. ¹Clearly irrelevant studies will be excluded during title and abstract
 335 screening. ²Reasons for exclusion during full text screening may be: full text not accessible, no
 336 primary data presented, exclusion criteria fulfilled.

337 Data extraction

338 Data will be extracted from all studies included after the full-text screening. The in-
 339 house software tool SciExtract will be used to compile the data based on pre-coded
 340 options and free text. SciExtract allows us to compile the data in a highly structured
 341 way, and it supports organizing and managing the workflow, tracking changes, and
 342 storing the pdfs and extracted data. We will include relevant publication details,
 343 information on the population, chemical exposure, health outcome(s) and study design
 344 (Table 4, SI_draft data extraction code book).

345 After setting up data extraction templates in SciExtract, we will test the process with a
 346 defined set of references. At least two team members will independently extract data
 347 from a subset of studies and compare the results. Potential conflicts will be discussed
 348 and either resolved directly, or input from an additional team member will be called in.
 349 After this testing process, data extraction templates may be revised, and an additional
 350 guidance document will be prepared to facilitate consistent data extraction. The data

351 from the remaining references will be extracted by one team member and the option to
 352 call for an additional opinion will be implemented in the task management process. If
 353 necessary, the guidance document will be refined during the data extraction process
 354 and all team members will be regularly informed about potential edits. It will be ensured
 355 that updates will not conflict with existing data (e.g., the addition of response options to
 356 a predefined selection is often possible). The option to exclude references during data
 357 extraction will be permitted to revise decisions regarding a study's eligibility made
 358 during the full-text screening process. Such decisions will always require review by and
 359 agreement from a second team member.

360 Table 4. Data that will be reported based on pre-coded options.

Data category	Data captured
Bibliographic information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Author(s) • Title • Year of publication • Journal • URL • Volume • Issue • Pages • DOI • Abstract
Information on studied population	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Population type • Number of participants • Biological sex • Ethnicity • Socio-economic status • Age at which exposure was measured • Age at which health outcome was measured • Country of investigated population • Special risk population and comparator group
Chemical information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chemical name(s) • CAS RN

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optional: Chemical group • Multiple exposures • Detection frequencies
Health outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Predefined categories based on the SCOD* (cancer, cardiovascular diseases, reproductive disorders, brain-related disorders, immunological disorders, metabolic diseases)
Study design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Predefined categories, such as cross-sectional and longitudinal studies

361 *If an FCC is linked to more than one disease cluster, several database entries will be generated
362 reflecting these multiple associations.

363 In many cases, the CAS RN is not provided for a given chemical in an epidemiological
364 study. Therefore, the chemical names will be matched to CAS RNs in a post-processing
365 step, following a previously described process (Geueke et al., 2023). A critical appraisal
366 of the studies and extracted data will not be included, which is in line with the
367 methodology of systematic evidence mapping.

368 Data analysis and presentation

369 The extracted information will be linked to a chemical index of FCCs, the references,
370 and a pre-coded overview of human health outcomes. It will be presented graphically as
371 an interactive dashboard using PowerBI, including diagrams, heat maps, bar plots
372 and/or tables to visualize the main outcomes. The focus will be placed on the link
373 between human exposure to FCCs and associated health outcomes. Integrated filters
374 will allow the selection and highlighting of specific information, e.g., in relation to study
375 design, population types, chemical groups, and the publication year. For filtered data
376 sets, the underlying references will always be linked. A narrative summary in the form of
377 a peer-reviewed scientific manuscript will further explain the presented results and
378 provide background information.

379 The systematic evidence map linking FCCs to human health effects will provide a
380 comprehensive overview of the existing literature and will complement the systematic
381 evidence map on migrating and extractable FCCs (Geueke et al., 2023), the systematic
382 overview of the presence of FCCs in humans (Geueke, Parkinson, et al., 2024), and the

383 systematic evidence map of human health effects of plastic chemicals (Seewoo et al.,
384 2023). Together, these sources will provide a better understanding of the human health
385 effects of chemical exposure from FCMs, highlight knowledge gaps and identify areas
386 for further investigation.

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435 **Abbreviations**

436 CHMS – Canadian Health Measures Survey

437 FCA – food contact article

438 FCC – food contact chemical

439 FCM – food contact material

440 HBM4EU – European Human Biomonitoring Initiative

441 ICD – International Classification of Diseases

442 KONEHS – Korean National Environmental Health Survey

443 NHANES – National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey

444 PECOS – population, exposure, comparator, outcome, study design

445 SAB – scientific advisory group

446 SCOD – Six Clusters of Disease

447 References

- 448 Carlson, L. M., Christensen, K., Sagiv, S. K., Rajan, P., Klocke, C. R., Lein, P. J., Coffman,
449 E., Shaffer, R. M., Yost, E. E., Arzuaga, X., Factor-Litvak, P., Sergeev, A., Toborek,
450 M., Bloom, M. S., Trgovcich, J., Jusko, T. A., Robertson, L., Meeker, J. D., Keating,
451 A. F., Blain, R., Silva, R. A., Snow, S., Lin, C., Shipkowski, K., Ingle, B., & Lehmann,
452 G. M. (2023). A systematic evidence map for the evaluation of noncancer health
453 effects and exposures to polychlorinated biphenyl mixtures. *Environ Res*, 220,
454 115148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2022.115148>.
- 455 EU 2024/3190. Commission Regulation (EU) 2024/3190 of 19 December 2024 on the
456 use of bisphenol A (BPA) and other bisphenols and bisphenol derivatives with
457 harmonised classification for specific hazardous properties in certain materials
458 and articles intended to come into contact with food, amending Regulation (EU)
459 No 10/2011 and repealing Regulation (EU) 2018/213. *Official Journal of the*
460 *European Union*.
- 461 EU 2025/40. Regulation (EU) 2025/40 of the European Parliament and of the Council of
462 19 December 2024 on packaging and packaging waste, amending Regulation
463 (EU) 2019/1020 and Directive (EU) 2019/904, and repealing Directive 94/62/EC.
464 *Official Journal of the European Union*.
- 465 EU 2025/351. Commission Regulation (EU) 2025/351 of 21 February 2025 amending
466 Regulation (EU) No 10/2011 on plastic materials and articles intended to come
467 into contact with food, amending Regulation (EU) 2022/1616 on recycled plastic
468 materials and articles intended to come into contact with foods, and repealing
469 Regulation (EC) No 282/2008, and amending Regulation (EC) No 2023/2006 on
470 good manufacturing practice for materials and articles intended to come into
471 contact with food as regards recycled plastic and other matters related to quality
472 control and manufacturing of plastic materials and articles intended to come
473 into contact with food. *Official Journal of the European Union*.
- 474 Food Packaging Forum. Food Contact Chemicals & Human Health Project. Retrieved
475 from: <https://foodpackagingforum.org/resources/research-projects/fcch-project>
476 Accessed 6 January 2025.
- 477 Food Packaging Forum. (2024). FCChumon Database. Retrieved from:
478 <https://foodpackagingforum.org/resources/databases/fcchumon> Accessed 6
479 January 2025.
- 480 Food Packaging Forum. (2025). FCCmigex Database v3.0. Retrieved from:
481 <https://foodpackagingforum.org/resources/databases/fccmigex> Accessed 30
482 June 2025.
- 483 Geueke, B., Groh, K. J., Maffini, M. V., Martin, O. V., Boucher, J. M., Chiang, Y.-T., Gwosdz,
484 F., Jieh, P., Kassotis, C. D., Łańska, P., Myers, J. P., Odermatt, A., Parkinson, L. V.,
485 Schreier, V. N., Srebny, V., Zimmermann, L., Scheringer, M., & Muncke, J. (2023).
486 Systematic evidence on migrating and extractable food contact chemicals: Most
487 chemicals detected in food contact materials are not listed for use. *Crit Rev*
488 *Food Sci Nutr*, 63(28), 9425–9435.
489 <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2022.2067828>.

- 490 Geueke, B., & Parkinson, L. V. (2024). S112 | FCCMIGEX | List of Migrating & Extractable
491 Food Contact Chemicals (FCCmigex) by PPF. *Zenodo*,
492 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10551195>.
- 493 Geueke, B., Parkinson, L. V., Groh, K. J., Kassotis, C. D., Maffini, M. V., Martin, O. V.,
494 Zimmermann, L., Scheringer, M., & Muncke, J. (2024). Evidence for widespread
495 human exposure to food contact chemicals. *J Expo Sci Environ Epidemiol*.
496 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41370-024-00718-2>.
- 497 Goodes, L. M., Wong, E. V. S., Alex, J., Mofflin, L., Toshniwal, P., Brunner, M., Solomons,
498 T., White, E., Choudhury, O., Seewoo, B. J., Mulders, Y. R., Dale, T., Newman, H. J.,
499 Naveed, A., Lowe, A. B., Hendrie, D. V., Symeonides, C., & Dunlop, S. A. (2022). A
500 scoping review protocol on in vivo human plastic exposure and health impacts.
501 *Syst Rev*, 11(1), 137. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-022-02010-6>.
- 502 Groh, K. J., Geueke, B., Chirsir, P., Schymanski, E. L., & Muncke, J. (2022). S77 | FCCDB |
503 Food Contact Chemicals Database v5.0. *Zenodo*,
504 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7304977>.
- 505 Groh, K. J., Geueke, B., Martin, O., Maffini, M., & Muncke, J. (2021). Overview of
506 intentionally used food contact chemicals and their hazards. *Environ Int*, 150,
507 106225. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.106225>.
- 508 Hanegraaf, P., Wondimu, A., Mosselman, J. J., de Jong, R., Abogunrin, S., Queiros, L.,
509 Lane, M., Postma, M. J., Boersma, C., & van der Schans, J. (2024). Inter-reviewer
510 reliability of human literature reviewing and implications for the introduction of
511 machine-assisted systematic reviews: a mixed-methods review. *BMJ open*,
512 14(3), e076912. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2023-076912>.
- 513 Hao, Y., Wang, Y., Yan, L., Xu, X., Chen, D., Zhao, Y., & Qiao, J. (2023). Synthetic Phenolic
514 Antioxidants and Their Metabolites in Follicular Fluid and Association with
515 Diminished Ovarian Reserve: A Case-Control Study. *Environ Health Perspect*,
516 131(6), 67005. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp11309>.
- 517 Howard, B. E., Phillips, J., Tandon, A., Maharana, A., Elmore, R., Mav, D., Sedykh, A.,
518 Thayer, K., Merrick, B. A., Walker, V., Rooney, A., & Shah, R. R. (2020). SWIFT-
519 Active Screener: Accelerated document screening through active learning and
520 integrated recall estimation. *Environ Int*, 138, 105623.
521 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.105623>.
- 522 Martínez-Ibarra, A., Martínez-Razo, L. D., MacDonald-Ramos, K., Morales-Pacheco, M.,
523 Vázquez-Martínez, E. R., López-López, M., Rodríguez Dorantes, M., & Cerbón, M.
524 (2021). Multisystemic alterations in humans induced by bisphenol A and
525 phthalates: Experimental, epidemiological and clinical studies reveal the need
526 to change health policies. *Environ Pollution*, 271, 116380.
527 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.116380>.
- 528 Minderoo Foundation. Plastic Health Map. Retrieved from:
529 <https://r.flo.minderoo.org/Systematic-Evidence-Map/> Accessed 6 January 2025.
- 530 Moher, D., Shamseer, L., Clarke, M., Ghersi, D., Liberati, A., Petticrew, M., Shekelle, P., &
531 Stewart, L. A. (2015). Preferred reporting items for systematic review and meta-
532 analysis protocols (PRISMA-P) 2015 statement. *Syst Rev*, 4(1), 1.
533 <https://doi.org/10.1186/2046-4053-4-1>.
- 534 Muncke, J., Andersson, A.-M., Backhaus, T., Belcher, S. M., Boucher, J. M., Carney
535 Almroth, B., Collins, T. J., Geueke, B., Groh, K. J., Heindel, J. J., von Hippel, F. A.,
536 Legler, J., Maffini, M. V., Martin, O. V., Peterson Myers, J., Nadal, A., Nerin, C.,

537 Soto, A. M., Trasande, L., Vandenberg, L. N., Wagner, M., Zimmermann, L.,
538 Thomas Zoeller, R., & Scheringer, M. (2023). A vision for safer food contact
539 materials: Public health concerns as drivers for improved testing. *Environ Int*,
540 180, 108161. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2023.108161>.

541 Muncke, J., Andersson, A. M., Backhaus, T., Boucher, J. M., Carney Almroth, B., Castillo
542 Castillo, A., Chevrier, J., Demeneix, B. A., Emmanuel, J. A., Fini, J. B., Gee, D.,
543 Geueke, B., Groh, K., Heindel, J. J., Houlihan, J., Kassotis, C. D., Kwiatkowski, C.
544 F., Lefferts, L. Y., Maffini, M. V., Martin, O. V., Myers, J. P., Nadal, A., Nerin, C.,
545 Pelch, K. E., Fernández, S. R., Sargis, R. M., Soto, A. M., Trasande, L.,
546 Vandenberg, L. N., Wagner, M., Wu, C., Zoeller, R. T., & Scheringer, M. (2020).
547 Impacts of food contact chemicals on human health: a consensus statement.
548 *Environ Health*, 19(1), 25. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12940-020-0572-5>.

549 Muncke, J., Backhaus, T., Geueke, B., Maffini Maricel, V., Martin Olwenn, V., Myers John,
550 P., Soto Ana, M., Trasande, L., Trier, X., & Scheringer, M. (2017). Scientific
551 Challenges in the Risk Assessment of Food Contact Materials. *Environ Health*
552 *Perspect*, 125(9), 095001. <https://doi.org/10.1289/EHP644>.

553 Nerin, C., Alfaro, P., Aznar, M., & Domeño, C. (2013). The challenge of identifying non-
554 intentionally added substances from food packaging materials: A review. *Anal*
555 *Chim Acta*, 775, 14–24.
556 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2013.02.028>.

557 Nerín, C., Bourdoux, S., Faust, B., Gude, T., Lesueur, C., Simat, T., Stoermer, A., Van
558 Hoek, E., & Oldring, P. (2022). Guidance in selecting analytical techniques for
559 identification and quantification of non-intentionally added substances (NIAS) in
560 food contact materials (FCMS). *Food Addit Contam Part A Chem Anal Control*
561 *Expo Risk Assess*, 39(3), 620–643.
562 <https://doi.org/10.1080/19440049.2021.2012599>.

563 Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D.,
564 Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., Brennan, S. E., Chou, R., Glanville, J.,
565 Grimshaw, J. M., Hróbjartsson, A., Lalu, M. M., Li, T., Loder, E. W., Mayo-Wilson,
566 E., McDonald, S., McGuinness, L. A., Stewart, L. A., Thomas, J., Tricco, A. C.,
567 Welch, V. A., Whiting, P., & Moher, D. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: an
568 updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *Bmj*, 372, n71.
569 <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>.

570 Payne-Sturges, D. C., Taiwo, T. K., Ellickson, K., Mullen, H., Tchangalova, N., Anderko, L.,
571 Chen, A., & Swanson, M. (2023). Disparities in Toxic Chemical Exposures and
572 Associated Neurodevelopmental Outcomes: A Scoping Review and Systematic
573 Evidence Map of the Epidemiological Literature. *Environ Health Perspect*, 131(9),
574 96001. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp11750>.

575 Pelch, K. E., Reade, A., Kwiatkowski, C. F., Merced-Nieves, F. M., Cavalier, H., Schultz,
576 K., Wolffe, T., & Varshavsky, J. (2022). The PFAS-Tox Database: A systematic
577 evidence map of health studies on 29 per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances.
578 *Environ Int*, 167, 107408. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2022.107408>.

579 Radke, E. G., Wright, J. M., Christensen, K., Lin, C. J., Goldstone, A. E., Lemeris, C., &
580 Thayer, K. A. (2022). Epidemiology Evidence for Health Effects of 150 per- and
581 Polyfluoroalkyl Substances: A Systematic Evidence Map. *Environ Health*
582 *Perspect*, 130(9), 96003. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp11185>.

- 583 Ricolfi, L., Vendl, C., Bräunig, J., Taylor, M. D., Hesselson, D., Gregory Neely, G., Lagisz,
584 M., & Nakagawa, S. (2024). A research synthesis of humans, animals, and
585 environmental compartments exposed to PFAS: A systematic evidence map and
586 bibliometric analysis of secondary literature. *Environ Int*, 190, 108860.
587 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2024.108860>.
- 588 Schreier, V. N., Çörek, E., Appenzeller-Herzog, C., Brüscheweiler, B. J., Geueke, B., Wilks,
589 M. F., Schilter, B., Muncke, J., Simat, T. J., Smieško, M., Roth, N., & Odermatt, A.
590 (2023). Evaluating the food safety and risk assessment evidence-base of
591 polyethylene terephthalate oligomers: A systematic evidence map. *Environ Int*,
592 176, 107978. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2023.107978>.
- 593 Seewoo, B. J., Goodes, L. M., Mofflin, L., Mulders, Y. R., Wong, E. V. S., Toshniwal, P.,
594 Brunner, M., Alex, J., Johnston, B., Elagali, A., Gozt, A., Lyle, G., Choudhury, O.,
595 Solomons, T., Symeonides, C., & Dunlop, S. A. (2023). The plastic health map: A
596 systematic evidence map of human health studies on plastic-associated
597 chemicals. *Environ Int*, 181, 108225.
598 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2023.108225>.
- 599 Shirke, A. V., Radke, E. G., Lin, C., Blain, R., Vetter, N., Lemeris, C., Hartman, P.,
600 Hubbard, H., Angrish, M., Arzuaga, X., Congleton, J., Davis, A., Dishaw, L. V.,
601 Jones, R., Judson, R., Kaiser, J. P., Kraft, A., Lizarraga, L., Noyes, P. D., Patlewicz,
602 G., Taylor, M., Williams, A. J., Thayer, K. A., & Carlson, L. M. (2024). Expanded
603 Systematic Evidence Map for Hundreds of Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances
604 (PFAS) and Comprehensive PFAS Human Health Dashboard. *Environ Health*
605 *Perspect*, 132(2), 26001. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp13423>.
- 606 Sinclair, S., & Rockwell, G. (2024). Voyant Tools. Retrieved from: <https://voyant-tools.org/>
607 Accessed 6 November 2024.
- 608 Symeonides, C., Aromataris, E., Mulders, Y., Dizon, J., Stern, C., Barker, T. H., Whitehorn,
609 A., Pollock, D., Marin, T., & Dunlop, S. (2024). An Umbrella Review of Meta-
610 Analyses Evaluating Associations between Human Health and Exposure to Major
611 Classes of Plastic-Associated Chemicals. *Ann Glob Health*.
612 <https://doi.org/10.5334/aogh.4459>.
- 613 Whaley, P., Aiassa, E., Beausoleil, C., Beronius, A., Bilotta, G., Boobis, A., de Vries, R.,
614 Hanberg, A., Hoffmann, S., Hunt, N., Kwiatkowski, C. F., Lam, J., Lipworth, S.,
615 Martin, O., Randall, N., Rhomberg, L., Rooney, A. A., Schünemann, H. J., Wikoff,
616 D., Wolffe, T., & Halsall, C. (2020). Recommendations for the conduct of
617 systematic reviews in toxicology and environmental health research (COSTER).
618 *Environ Int*, 143, 105926. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.105926>.
- 619 World Health Organisation. (2022). ICD-11 International Classification of Diseases for
620 Mortality and Morbidity Statistics. *Reference Guide*.
621 <https://doi.org/https://icdcdn.who.int/icd11referenceguide/en/html/index.html>.
- 622 Yost, E. E., Galizia, A., Kapraun, D. F., Persad, A. S., Vulimiri, S. V., Angrish, M., Lee, J. S.,
623 & Druwe, I. L. (2021). Health Effects of Naphthalene Exposure: A Systematic
624 Evidence Map and Analysis of Potential Considerations for Dose-Response
625 Evaluation. *Environ Health Perspect*, 129(7), 76002.
626 <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp7381>.
- 627 Zhang, L., Louie, A., Rigutto, G., Guo, H., Zhao, Y., Ahn, S., Dahlberg, S., Sholinbeck, M.,
628 & Smith, M. T. (2023). A systematic evidence map of chronic inflammation and
629 immunosuppression related to per- and polyfluoroalkyl substance (PFAS)

630 exposure. *Environ Res*, 220, 115188.
631 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2022.115188>.
632 Zhu, Y., Liu, K., Guo, J., Yang, J., & Su, Y. (2024). Bisphenol A exposure and thyroid
633 dysfunction during pregnancy: A systematic review. *Reprod Toxicol*, 129, 108680.
634 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.reprotox.2024.108680>.
635 Zimmermann, L., Scheringer, M., Geueke, B., Boucher, J. M., Parkinson, L. V., Groh, K. J.,
636 & Muncke, J. (2022). Implementing the EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability:
637 The case of food contact chemicals of concern. *J Hazard Mater*, 437, 129167.
638 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2022.129167>.
639